

74% CO₂ reduction using optimised steel Design of bridges for approach lights to Nuuk Airport

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ABSTRACT

Optimisation of steel structures is an important part in the goal of reducing the CO₂ footprint. The new 260 m long bridges for approach light are an example of optimisation of the structure compared with the design by KAIR the owner of Nuuk Airport, Greenland. In the new design several other advantages for the project have been included and architects have been involved, since the bridges have a significant visual impact seen from Nuuk city.

The runway is being extended. Due to limited space two steel bridges are built to support the approach lights and to have an easy access during maintenance. Each of the two bridges consists of four lattice towers. A walkway and the lights will be positioned on top of the bridge lattice. The length of the bridge is 260 m, and the height of the towers varies between 25-65 m.

In Greenland the wind and ice load are predominant, and it is therefore vital to reduce wind drag on tall and slender structures. Consequently, circular tubes are used instead of angle profiles.

All lattice structures are made by steel tubes to reduce the wind load and utilise the material as much as possible. Connections are done by bolts connections. The supports of the towers are done by rock anchor and a minimum amount of concrete.

Due to minimising the wind drag of the structure and utilising the good quality bedrock, it has been possible to save 74% of the CO₂ footprint compared to the original proposal.

Keywords: Sustainability, Bridge Structures, Optimisation

1 INTRODUCTION

In 2016 it was decided to expand the runway of the Nuuk airport from 950m to 2200m to be able to receive the bigger airplanes that cross the Atlantic. The owner of the airport is Kalaallit Airports (KAIR), who owns the airports in Greenland. The area where the airport is situated is close to a mountain and a lot of blasting is needed to make the expanded runway. As much as 6 Mio. cubic meters of rock needed to be blasted to make space for the runway.

Unfortunately, there is not enough space for the approach lights outside the runway and thus KAIR decides to build two 260 m long bridges to support the approach light. An alternative to this solution is to build separate towers for each approach light, but this makes the maintenance of the lights more difficult. Consequently, they chose to build the two new bridges – one to the south of the runway and one to the north.

A preliminary design of the bridges was proposed by KAIR. However, during the detailed design of the bridges it was clear that the structures could be optimised. The bridges are planned to be onshore – however some of the lights on the north bridge are almost over the coastline. In the Nuuk area the tide is around 5m.

A requirement of breakable towers above the deck with a height of more than 12m were given by the authorities – but later this requirement was removed.

Fig. 1. Overview of the location of the runway and the bridges for the approach lights

2 LAYOUT

2.1 Layout by the owner

The original design from KAIR consists of 17 lattice towers supporting the bridge deck. The lattice is mainly made from angle profiles. A side view of the North Bridge is seen in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Owner's design, North Bridge

A 3D model of the original bridge design has been made to calculate the utilisation of the main members in the bridge. The 3D overview of North Bridge is shown in *Fig. 3* where the complex layout of the different towers is clearly visible.

Fig. 3. Utilisations of the owner’s design, North Bridge

2.2 Architect competition

The South Bridge is visible from most of Nuuk and consequently it is important to make a simpler and more harmonic aesthetic layout of the bridge. An architect competition has been conducted involving two recognised architect companies. Eventually, Gottlieb Paludan Architects was chosen due to a more harmonic look – as well as a reduction of the carbon footprint. Their proposal is shown in *Fig. 4 b*).

The towers and the bridge are made of tubes that has a smaller width than the angle profiles in the owner’s design. Tubes has proven to be superior to angle profiles when the goal is to reduce costs and CO2 footprint (1).

The square towers are made as special type of V-lattice – a diamond pattern – where the four diagonals meet at the same location. This special pattern was first used for the new overhead line, Thor, that is being built on the west side of Jutland, Denmark in these years (2).

Fig. 4. a) Original design, South Bridge; b) Gottlieb Paludan proposal, South Bridge

2.3 Arguments for improving the design

Looking at the given design from the owner, there were some areas where the design could be improved in order to reduce the quantity of materials, decreasing the costs and improve the sustainability. One of the areas was the concrete foundations. This was mainly designed as gravity foundations. However, there were only a few rock anchors. In Greenland it is complex to make concrete foundations in this scale – one of the foundations has the dimensions 7m x 7m x 9m. Each of these foundations were replaced by 4 smaller concrete foundations with rock anchors of steel – one for each leg. A total of 800 concrete trucks were needed to build the foundations – It is difficult to get that much concrete in Greenland.

The purpose of the bridge is to hold the lamps for the approach lights. The owner's design was based on breakable towers that could fold in order for the approach lights to be reached from the top of bridge deck. This is a complex situation and since it was actually not a requirement, the bridge deck was lifted up to just below level of the approach light as seen in *Fig. 4 b*). In this way it is much easier to service the lamps.

The design of the original bridge is dominated by the 17 towers and some of them were placed very close to the coastline. The number of towers could be reduced to 4 (6 in the design by the architect). In this way it was also possible to reduce the amount of safety rail from 1200m in the owner's design to around one quarter.

3 OVERALL STATIC DESIGN

The new bridges consist of four squared towers each with a height ranging from 25 to 65m depending on the terrain profile underneath the bridge. These load-bearing towers support a 260m long horizontal lattice bridge deck that supports a walkway and the approach lights. About halfway along the bridge a cross-bridge is located with a total width of 30.5m. The cross-bridge is necessary to support the mandatory cross-lights in the approach light system. Finally, the bridge is supported at the start of the bridge directly on the terrain level. A side view of the bridge is presented in *Fig. 5*.

Fig. 5. Side view of the bridge

The towers are installed directly on the bedrock by concrete blocks that are secured to the bedrock by rock anchors at each leg. The landing foundation is made in such a way that it is only taking the vertical load and horizontal load perpendicular to the direction of the bridge. The bridge is free to move in the longitudinal direction at the landing support to avoid large forces from temperature variations.

The lattice in the towers and the bridge deck is made as a V-lattice and all members are steel tubes. Connections between the diagonals and the legs are made as bolt connections.

4 DETAILED DESIGN

4.1 FE model

A full 3D model for each of the two bridges is made including all the main structural members. The models are made in ROSAP which is an in-house developed FE program. In this model the loads on the bridge such as wind, ice and temperature are applied and afterwards combined according to the methods described in the Eurocodes. The structural capacity and utilisation are afterward determined along with the deformation of the bridge.

Fig. 6. 3D FE model of the South Bridge (ROSAP)

Fig. 7. Loads applied on the main structure in the FE model

4.2 Main structural members

The lattice structure in the final design is made from steel tubes, which are excellent in utilising the steel strength in a buckling scenario. The original design from the owner is mainly built by angle profiles. However, angle bars are in many ways not as good as the tube profile. To illustrate the difference between the two profile types, an example is made. Both profile types have similar weight and therefore same section steel area. The cross-section of the profiles is presented in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Example of an angle profile (L 120x120x12) and a tube profile (Ø114.3x8) with similar weight

The properties of the angle profile and the tube profile are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Properties of the angle profile and the tube profile

Profile	Weight	Moment of inertia about weak axis	Drag coefficient
L120x120x12	21.6 kg/m	$1.52 \cdot 10^6 \text{ mm}^4$	~2.1
Ø114.3x8	21.0 kg/m	$3.79 \cdot 10^6 \text{ mm}^4$	~1.2

The following advantages by using tubes can be observed:

- *Tubes have a greater moment of inertia compared to angle profiles with similar weight. In this example the bending stiffness is about 2.5 times higher. The bending stiffness is important in a compression scenario where buckling can occur, which is the case for lattice structures.*
- *The drag factor is about 0.6 times lower for tube members compared to flat elements such as the angle profiles. This reduces the overall wind load on the structure and hence reducing the required member size, foundation capacity etc.*
- *It is easier to get large tube profiles compared to angle profiles. Hence, tube profiles are more suitable for large structures.*

In the evaluation of the wind load on the structure the knowledge from tower industry has been used including wind tunnel tests of lattice structures (3).

The downside of tube profiles is that connections are more complex to produce as they require gusset plates on both the leg members and diagonal members. For angle profiles it is possible to simply bolt the members together without introducing gusset plates.

4.3 Tower lattice type

The lattice in the towers is design with a *diamond* pattern. Instead of having only two diagonals at one location for each leg similar to a traditional v-lattice configuration, the diagonal members meet at each intersection at the leg. This creates a well-looking pattern that can appear more transparent when looked at 45° angle compared to the side of the tower. The lattice of the tower is seen in *Fig. 9*.

Fig. 9. Diamond lattice pattern in the tower

4.4 Joints and walkway

All members in the lattice are assembled by flange connections or *fork* connections. In this way it is possible to transport all the members to site by containers. The advantage of the fork connection is that it is symmetric which reduce the moment from eccentricities. Examples of the joints are seen in *Fig. 10*.

Fig. 10. Examples of the joints in the bridge

4.5 Foundations

The foundation for the original bridge design is made as gravity foundations placed on the bedrock at each tower. Since the foundation must be able to withstand the overturning moment from the bridge, the gravity foundations are be up to 9m high and with a footprint of 7x7m in order to have sufficient weight, as seen in *Fig. 11 a*). However, concrete in Greenland is relatively difficult to get as the production capacity is low which makes it preferable to reduce the concrete volume.

For the new design the bedrock has been used actively by installing rock anchors. Thus, it is possible to transfer the tension force from the leg of the tower directly to the bedrock. To reduce the concrete amount further, the foundation is only installed at each of the four legs instead of covering the entire footprint of the tower. Hence, the foundation blocks are 2.2m x 2.2m x 1.4m with 8 pcs. Ø54mm rock anchors per foundation block with a length of 7.5m. The foundation is seen in *Fig. 11 b*).

Fig. 11. a) Original gravity foundation design; b) New foot foundation at each leg with rock anchors

5 ERECTION

Since the lattice sections are made by tube members bolted together, a lot of assembly work is required at the site. The members are transported to Nuuk by containers, which are stored closed to the site. First the towers sections are assembled in 10m sections. These sections are lifted individually and placed on top of each other as seen in *Fig. 12 a*) and *b*). After the towers are erected the bridge sections are assembled into sections with a length of up to 60m. The bridge section is lifted by two cranes and placed on top of the towers as seen in *Fig. 12 c*). The walkway section is already installed on top of the bridge deck before the lifting to avoid as much work high above ground as possible.

Fig. 12. a) Lifting of tower sections; b) Assembly of the sections; c) Lifting of the 60m bridge section

6 MATERIAL AND CO2 SAVINGS

A number of different decisions have been taken in order to reduce the use of materials and reduce the carbon footprint. The design loads on the bridges are determined by the wind and ice load. It is therefore important to reduce the wind and ice load as much as possible.

The wind climate around the Nuuk airport has been investigated and it is possible to reduce the wind load in the direction perpendicular to the bridge. The design gust wind at the level of the bridge deck reaches 80 m/s. In the climate investigation the determination of the design ice load has also been conducted.

Another change that reduced the load is the choice of round tubes instead of angle profiles as well as reducing the number of towers.

The savings result in significant reduction of the costs for both the contractor and the owner.

The most important change of the design is the change of foundation principles from large gravitation foundation to rock anchors with small concrete foundation at each leg.

Table 2. Material and CO2 saving

	Original design	New design
Steel Weight	750 t	521 t
Concrete volume	6300 m ³	433 m ³
Reinforcement	300 t	55 t
CO2 emission	6194 t	1610 t
CO2 reduction	-	74%

In total a reduction of 30% on steel has been reached, but the largest reduction is in concrete and reinforcement where a 93% weight reduction is reached resulting in a reduction on the carbon footprint of 74%.

7 CONCLUSION

The bridges for approach light have been redesigned to improve the functionality and to reduce the carbon footprint significantly by saving materials - both steel and concrete.

The functionality has been improved on several parameters:

- *Access to the lamps in the approach lights.*
- *Less ladders with fall protection.*
- *No foundations on the boarder of the coastline.*
- *Designed by architects resulting in a more aesthetic design.*

The savings on materials are mainly due to a change in the foundation principles using rock anchors instead for concrete gravity foundations. Furthermore the overall steel design has been changed from angle profiles to steel tubes. This reduces the wind load significantly and increases the buckling capacity.

Finally, the static system has been changed with considerably less towers making the overall load much less.

In total it resulted in a reduction of the carbon footprint of 74%.

Fig. 13. View of the runway looking from the south toward north

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